

DETERMINANTS OF THE INTEREST FOR USING SHARIA DIGITAL BANKING SERVICES ON GENERATION Z IN MALANG CITY

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to analyze the factors that influence interest in using sharia digital banking services and their influence on Generation Z in Malang City. This analysis uses four variables: security variable (X1), convenience variable (X2), trust variable (X3), and interest variable (Y). The type of research used is quantitative with a descriptive approach. Primary data in this study used a questionnaire distributed via Google Forms. The population in this study was Generation Z in Malang City and the research sample was 120 respondents. The sampling method in this research used proportional random sampling with probability sampling techniques. Data analysis and testing techniques use the SPSS 24 application. Based on the research results, it show that the variables of security, convenience, and trust have a significant effect on interest in using sharia digital banking services among Generation Z in Malang City. It can be concluded that if one of the three independent variables decreases, then interest in using sharia digital banking services will decrease.

Keywords: *Security, Comfort, Trust, Interest, Service Digital Banking, Generation Z*

I. INTRODUCTION

Rate development technology Which dynamic And the more fast influence activity public Which cause exists transformation technology. Technology information own various field technology in accordance need Which aim For increase efficiency, comfort and convenience in every aspect of human life. The impact of technology digital is very big on human behavior such as paying using non-cash or *digital payment*, even though in the past people only rely on cash payments. Obtained from Bank Indonesia (BI) which shows that total digital transactions increased by 35.79% in the third quarter of 2022. In 2022 the total value of electronic transactions increase 32.27% of the year to year up to reach Rp. 404 trillion (Warjiyo, 2022).

Banking sharia present as receptacle which help increase interest as well as public trust in utilizing sharia *digital banking services*. Therefore banking sharia must practical, innovative, And creative so that public interested for utilize service *digital*

banking sharia. Besides That banking sharia must understand what which needed by society, especially Generation Z, so that a sense of trust and comfort is instilled in utilise service *digital banking sharia*. Due interest use is main factor in banking industry sharia (Ida *et al.*, 2020).

The development of the world's population and the support of economic growth gave birth to various generations, one of which is Generation Z. Generation Z or what we often call it Gen Z is generation first one know technology since early stage. According to Wafa & Soedarmadi (2021) Generation Z are those born between 1995 – 2012, who own various characteristic And characteristics. They Also grow together with rapidly technology Which the more peaked (Alfaruqy, 2022). Generation Z Also known as man Which likes things that are instant and practical without requiring a lot of effort. Nowadays many people who use electronic money which is considered more effective and efficient in contrast to previous generations who used non-electronic money more often (Hamzah & Sukma, 2021).

As the largest Muslim population in the world, Indonesia has market share opportunities and progress economy finance sharia (Coal & Anggraini, 2022). Body Center Statistics explained that the population of Indonesia in mid-2023 will be 278 million soul. Based on 2022, Gen Z has the largest population compared to generations other, presented in following picture:

Picture 1
Population Resident Based on Generation Year 2022

Source: Body Center Statistics

The picture above shows that the population is based on generations, years 2022, namely Post Gen Z at 10.88%, Gen Z at 27.94%, Gen Y at 25.87%, Baby Boomers were 11.56%, and Pre Boomers were 1.87%. Can be interpreted as population most dominant on 2022 is Generation Z.

According to the Director General of Dukcapil, Zudan Arif Fakhrulloh, Generation Z own Lots opportunity And potential for industry banking sharia.

Besides That they considered responsible and prospective for the digitalization of sharia banking. According to the Services Authority Finance (OJK) share of the sharia financial market as of June 2022 was 10.41%, experiencing improvement than year previously, However If compared to with industry bank conventional is still further away. It can be concluded that people's interest in finance sharia Enough spelled out low compared to finance conventional. Matter This No in line with amount Muslim population by 86% of the total population Indonesia.

From the explanation above, it is stated that Generation Z has extraordinary potential for the progress of the sharia financial market share in the future. But not all Generation Z is interested in using sharia *digital banking services*. Because banking Sharia is known for its lack of innovation and low competitiveness compared to industry finance conventional. There is a number of factor Which become reason lack interest use service *digital sharia banking*, namely security, comfort, And trust.

According to Kehista *et al.*, (2023) security is a protection to source- physical source nor conceptual from threat human or natural. According to Triandi (2019) Information security in *digital banking services* is protective in various forms threat use ensure walking business, minimize risk, increase profit. Study conducted by Khotijah (2023) emphasized that there is a connection between security with an interest in using sharia *digital banking services*. However, this is contradictory with the study of Mukhtisar *et al.*, (2021) which explains that there is no relationship between security with interest use service *digital banking sharia*. With so para candidate customers Not yet Of course interest use service *digital banking sharia* although service the it's guaranteed to be safe.

Convenience is one important factor in interest in use, cause People really pay attention to convenience in transactions. According to Keliat, *et al* (2015) comfort is flavor comfortable Which embedded in a way born And inner on self somebody. If somebody feel comfortable use service *digital banking*, so they will use it repeatedly (Woelandari PG, *et al.*, 2019). In Rozi & Ziyad's research (2019) emphasized that there is a relationship between comfort and interest in using service *digital banking*. However compare backwards on study Pulungan (2022) Which explained that there was no influence of comfort on interest in using the service *digital banking*. So it can be said that if customers feel comfortable it is not necessarily them interest use *digital banking services sharia*.

Apart from security and comfort, other factors influence interest in using it Sharia *digital banking services* are trust. Trust is a belief can fulfill one's obligations and expectations, but not everything goes according to plan which are desired. In these conditions we must anticipate possible risks happen, with exists trust Which later party Which involved will willing For take responsibility for their actions (Priyono, 2017). The basis of trust can be: organizational reputation or relational experience (Rahmad *et al.*, 2017). In Woelandari's research P.G., *et al* (2019) confirm that's it there is relatedness between trust with interest use *digital banking services*. This is different from the research of Agustina *et al.*, (2018). explain that there is no relationship between trust and interest in using service *digital banking*.

Based on exposure on And a number of study previous, so need held re-examination of what factors influence interest in using services *digital banking Sharia* on Generation Z.

II. METHODOLOGY

Researchers use a descriptive qualitative approach with primary data in the form of questionnaire Which spread through. Population study that is all over Generation Z especially students in Malang City. Researchers used 120 samples originating from number of indicators $\times 5$ following a total of 24 questions, so $24 \times 5 = 120$ respondents (Hair, *et al* 2010). Probability sampling techniques and proportional random sampling methods are used in taking sample study This. On technique analysis data study use regression linear multiple.

Characteristics respondents is sign Which addressed to subject study so that objective research can in accordance hope. There is 120 respondents Which will spread in location study. This research has characteristics based on agency, gender, age, bank sharia used, and *digital banking services*. This is necessary in order to provide clarity from subject research that related with research purposes (Mujiaty *et al.*, 2022).

Table 1
Characteristics Respondent Based on Institution

Institution	Amount	Percentage
UIN Poor	70	85.3%
Univ. Brawijaya	18	15%
Univ. Country Poor	8	6.7%
Univ. Islam Poor	6	5%
Other	18	15%
Total	120	100%

Source: Data Processed Researcher, 2024

Based on characteristics on table 1 known that study This there is 120 respondents Which institution in UIN Poor a number 70 or 85.3%, Univ. Brawijaya a number 18 or 15%, Univ. Malang State amounted to 8 or 6.7%, Univ. Malang Islam is 6 or 5%, and others amounting to 18 or 15%. Based on the previous interpretation, it can be concluded that respondents the most dominant comes from agencies UIN Malang.

Table 2
Characteristics Respondent Based on Type Sex

Type Sex	Amount	Percentage
Man	33	27.5 %
Woman	87	72.5 %
Total	120	100%

Source: Data Processed Researcher, 2024

Based on characteristics on table 2 known that study This there is 120 respondents Which manifold sex that is man a number 33 or 27.5% And Woman a number 87 or 72.5%.

Table 3
Characteristics Respondent Based on Age

<u>Age</u>	<u>Total</u>	<u>Percentage</u>
17-21 year	62	51.7 %
22-26 year	58	48.3 %
Total	120	100%

Source: Data Processed Researcher, 2024

Based on characteristics on table 3 known that study This there is 120 respondents, namely 17-21 years old, 62 or 51.7% and 22-26 years old, 58 or 48.3%. It can be concluded that more respondents Lots on around 17-21 years old.

Table 4
Characteristics Respondent Based on Bank Sharia Used

<u>Name Bank</u>	<u>Amount</u>	<u>Percentage</u>
Bank Sharia Indonesia (BSI)	75	62.5 %
Bank Muamalat	8	6.7%
BCA Sharia	12	10%
Other	25	20.8%
Total	120	100%

Source: Data Processed by Researchers, 2024

Based on characteristics on table 4 known that study This there is 120 respondents who used sharia banks were BSI, 75 or 62.5%, Bank Muamalat a number 8 or 7.7%, BCA Sharia amount 12 or 10%, And other 25 or 20.8%. So that concluded that Many respondents use BSI in *digital banking* services.

Table 5
Characteristics Respondent Based on Services *Digital Banking* Yang Used

<u>Service</u>	<u>Amount</u>	<u>Percentage</u>
Mobile Banking	112	93.3%
Internet Banking	5	4.2%
SMS Banking	1	0.8%
Other	2	1.7%
Total	120	100%

Source: Data Processed Researcher, 2024

Based on characteristics on table 5 known that study This there is 120 respondents who used *digital banking services*, namely *mobile banking*, were 112 or 93.3%, *internet banking* 5 or 4.2%, *SMS banking* 1 or 0.8%, and others a number 2 or 1.7%. Can concluded that respondents dominant use *mobile banking* compared to service *digital banking* other.

III. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

There is a need for analysis and trials in this research in order to determine the validity and reliability so that known worthy or No worthy instrument data Which used. Before did it test data questionnaire shared moreover formerly to respondents with answer Which given score 1-5.

3.1 Data Instrument Test Test Validity

Test validity used For determine whether instrument data (questionnaire) can stated valid or No valid. With use mark sig 0.5 as well as condition If $r \text{ count} > r \text{ table}$ so indicator question can said valid. If $r \text{ count} < r \text{ table}$ so indicator question said to be invalid (Ghozali, 2018).

Based on validity tests on the variables security (X1), comfort (X2), trust (X3), and Interest (Y) with a total of 24 indicators, all of which have $r \text{ count} > r \text{ table}$, namely 0.178 so all the question indicator variable is said to be valid.

3.2 Test Reliability

This test is carried out to find out how similar the measurement results are to the object and the same data (Sugiyono, 2017). According to Ghozali (2016) an instrument is valuable *Cronbach's alpha* > 0.6 so stated reliable.

Table 6
Results Test Reliability

Amount <i>Cronbach's</i> indicator	<i>Alpha</i>	Ket
24	0.977	Reliable

Source: Data Processed by Researchers, 2024

Based on the results of the reliability test above with a *Cronbach's alpha* value > 0.6 , namely $0.977 > 0.6$ so can be stated 24 question indicator on study this is reliable.

3.3 Classical Assumption Test Test Normality

The normality test is used to test a statistical model, namely the independent variable and the dependent variable and whether these two variables are normally distributed or not (Ghozali, 2016). It is declared normal if the sig value is > 0.5 and this research uses a test *kolmogrov Smirnov* in statistical tests.

Table 7
Results Normality Test

Results Normality Test		
	Unstandardized Residual	Note
N	120	Data distribute normal
	0.200	Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)

Source: Data Processed Researcher, 2024

It is known from table 7 that the sig value in the normality test with the *Kolmogrov Smirnov test* using the *Monte Carlo method* of $0.200 > 0.05$, it can be stated that the data distribute in a way normal.

3.4 Test Multicollinearity

Test multicollinearity aim For know whether every variable in a way linear each other related or not. Tolerance value and *Variance Inflation Factro* (VIF) are two indicators Which can used For show test multicollinearity (Ghozali, 2016). If mark VIF < 10 so can stated not experienced multicollinearity or not dangerous.

Table 8
Results Test Multicollinearity

Model	VIF	Note
Security	1,002	No There is multicollinearity
Comfort	1,158	No There is multicollinearity
Trust	1,155	No There is multicollinearity

Source: Data Processed by Researchers, 2024

Based on test multicollinearity on on mark VIF For variable security (X 1) $1,002 < 10$, comfort (X2) $1.158 < 10$, and trust (X3) $1.155 < 10$. So it is concluded model regression on study this is not there is multicollinearity between variable free.

3.5 Test Heteroscedasticity

Test heteroscedasticity used For know difference variant And residuals between observation. If the calculated t value $< t$ table then it does not contain heteroscedasticity. Seen from probability of significance above 5% confidence. The following are the results of the heteroscedasticity test using SPSS 24.

Table 9
Results Test Heteroscedasticity

Model	VIF	Note
Security	0.796	No There is heteroscedasticity
Comfort	0.564	No There is heteroscedasticity
Trust	0.958	No There is heteroscedasticity

Source: Data Processed Researcher, 2024

From the heteroscedasticity test above using the Glejser method, the sig on the variable security as big as 0.796, comfort as big as 0.564, as well as amount of trust 0.958 Which the whole > 0.05 then study This does not experience heteroscedasticity.

3.6 Test Linear Regression Multiple

Test regression multiple linear used For determine whether variable independent there is influence two direction or more on the dependent variable with formula $Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + e$ (Ghozali, 2018).

Table 10
Results Test Regression Linear Multiple

Model	Unstandardized coefficients	
	B	Std. Error
Constant	1,302	0,971
Keamanan	0,297	0,603
Kenyamanan	0,296	0,109
Kepercayaan	0,695	0,112

Source: Data Processed Researcher, 2024

Obtained equality regression linear multiple as following

$$Y = 1,302 + 0.297X_1 + 0.296X_2 + 0.695X_3 + e$$

Interpretation equality regression on that is:

1. *Constant* value of interest (Y) is 1.302 which states that the variables are X1, X2, and X3 equals zero, namely security, comfort and trust, then interest in using is amounting to 1,302.
2. The X1 coefficient is 0.297 if there is an increase in the security variable by 1 level so interest use increases of 0.297 (29.7 percent) and vice versa.
3. The X2 coefficient is 0.296 if there is an increase in the comfort variable by 1% so interest use increases of 0.296 (29.6 percent) likewise on the contrary.
4. Coefficient X3 as big as 0.695 If happen improvement variable trust as big as 1% so interest use increases of 0.695 (69.5 percent) vice versa.

3.7 Hypothesis Testing Test t

Table 11 Results Test Q

Model	t	Sig	Note
Security	4,714	0,000	H 1 accepted
Comfort	2,716	0.008	H 2 accepted
Trust	6,180	0,000	H 3 accepted

Source: Data Processed Researcher, 2024

From table 11 can known that:

1. Mark t table > t count that is 4,714 > 1,981 as well as mark sig < 0.05 (0.000 < 0.05) so H 0 rejected and H 1 accepted.
2. Mark t table > t count that is 2,716 > 1,981 as well as mark sig < 0.05 (0.008 < 0.05) so H 0 rejected and H 2 accepted.

3. Mark $t_{table} > t_{count}$ that is $6,180 > 1,981$ as well as mark $sig < 0.05$ ($0.000 > 0.05$) so H_0 rejected and H_3 accepted.

Table 12
Results Test F

Model	F	Sig	Ket
<i>Regression residual total</i>	303,374	0,000	H_0 rejected, H_4

Based on table 12, the calculated f value $>$ table f (303.374) and the sig value is $0.000 < 0.05$ So it can be concluded that the variables security, comfort and trust influence Y in a way simultaneous so H_4 accepted.

3.8 Test Coefficient Determination

Table 13
Results Test Coefficient Determination

R	R-Square	Adjusted R Square
0.942	0.887	0.884

Source: Data Processed Researcher, 2024

Based on the results of the r test above, it can be stated that the value of the coefficient of determination (R^2) amounting to 0.884 or 88.4%, thus indicating that the independent variables have a good relationship strong with the dependent variable. The remaining 11.6% is influenced by other outside factors scope of this research. It can be concluded that there are other possible independent variables influence Generational interests Z in using the service sharia *digital banking*.

IV. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Based on study Which done related service use *digital banking* sharia regarding the factors that influence Generation Z's quantitative interest use data primary then it can be concluded that:

- 1) Study This based on test instrument data on variable indicator question stated valid and reliable Study This based on test assumptions classic on variable indicator question stated distribute normally, as well as variables security, comfort, And trust no experience multicollinearity And heteroscedasticity to interest Generation Z use sharia *digital banking* services.
- 2) Based on test linear regression multiple with equality $Y = 1,302 + 0.297X_1 + 0.296X_2 + 0.695X_3 + e$ with a constant value of 1.302 and β values of 0.297, 0.296, and 0.695, for every 1% increase, interest in using sharia *digital banking services will increase* increase vice versa.
- 3) Based on the T test, the variables security, comfort and trust have an influence partial to Generational interests Z uses service *digital sharia banking*.
- 4) Based on the F test, the variables security, comfort and trust have an

influence simultaneous to interest Generation Z using *digital services sharia banking*.

- 5) Based on the R test (determination efficiency), the R Square (R^2) is 0.884 or 88.4% is interpreted as determining the variables security, comfort and trust has a strong relationship with Generation Z's interest variable in using services sharia *digital banking*. The difference is 11.6% which can be influenced by other factors outside scope of research This.

Suggestion

Based on conclusion on that factors Which influence interest Generation Z in Malang City, the use of sharia *digital banking services* is quite strong. Suggested by researcher should party banking more notice And maintain quality service especially in *digital banking services*. On the other hand, further research needs to be conducted validate as well as consider variables other Which No related in study This.

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